

A Supervised ML–Diviner Approach for Thermal Emission Removal for M³ VIS–NIR Data: New Insights into Lunar Hydration. F. Colaiuta^{1,2}, F. Tosi², and F. Zambon² ¹Department of Physics, University of Rome “La Sapienza”, Piazzale Aldo Moro 2, 00185 Rome, Italy (federico.colaiuta@inaf.it), ²INAF – Istituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali (INAF-IAPS), Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, I-00133, Rome.

Introduction: Global mapping of lunar surface hydration requires extensive spatial coverage and hyperspectral observations spanning at least the 2.7–3.0 μm spectral range, where diagnostic OH/H₂O absorption features occur. The Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³) [1] dataset provides an optimal resource, combining broad spatial coverage with VIS–NIR spectral measurements (0.43–3.00 μm) acquired in the period 2008–2009 at multiple local solar times (LSTs), enabling investigation of diurnal variability.

Previous studies of lunar hydration using M³ data adopted independent approaches to remove the thermal emission component, which becomes significant beyond ~ 2.0 – 2.5 μm , depending on surface temperature at the time of acquisition. These approaches include (i) a laboratory-based semi-empirical correction [2] and (ii) thermophysical models (TPMs) coupled with a Hapke reflectance formulation to reconstruct both reflected and thermal contributions to the measured signal [3]. Both methods were calibrated and/or validated against observations from the Diviner instrument [4] onboard the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter.

Here we present an additional, fully independent thermal-removal method developed specifically for M³ data, potentially applicable to all VIS–NIR lunar hyperspectral datasets covering at least the 0.89–2.67 μm range. The introduction of this new correction scheme enables renewed local- and global-scale analyses of lunar surface hydration, enhancing the robustness of previous results (e.g., [3,5]) and/or providing further constraints on the formation, stability, and diurnal variability of OH/H₂O on the lunar surface.

The Lunar thermal Emission Neural Network Approach (LENNA): LENNA is a supervised ML approach based on a fully connected feed-forward neural network. The target is bolometric temperature, obtained by interpolating Diviner radiance data (downloaded from [6]) to the M³ spatial resolution and processing them following [7]. Spatially and temporally overlapping M³–Diviner data are selected within a 0.05 h window to minimize temporal mismatches.

Input features include latitude, normalized local solar time, topographically corrected incidence cosine, an albedo proxy (0.89–1.62 μm mean reflectance), reflectance factors at 2.54–2.67 μm (M³ channels 74–77), and the I/F spectral slope between 2.02 and 2.67 μm (M³ channels 60–77), targeting thermal residuals while limiting sensitivity to hydration bands. The network is trained on 19 ROIs and tested on 8 independent ROIs to assess spatial leakage [8]. Thermal removal is performed using the Hapke’s

radiative transfer formulation [9]. Results show high accuracy, precision, no evidence of systematic biases, and improved performance over the semi-empirical method in [2]. LENNA enables near-instantaneous temperature retrieval over large datasets, offering a fast and accurate alternative to advanced TPMs and laboratory-based methods. However, anisothermal effects at local scale are only partially accounted for, with noticeable deviations at incidence angles >65 – 70° , where temperatures fall below ~ 300 K and thermal emission shortward of 3.0 μm weakens.

Current results and future developments:

LENNA produces three main outputs: (i) Diviner-like bolometric temperature; (ii) effective directional spectral emissivity, modeled using Hapke’s radiative transfer formulation [9]; and (iii) thermally corrected reflectance spectra, enabling OH/H₂O analyses, here performed using the ESPAT parameter [5]. At this stage, we have performed LENNA on part of the OP2C data [1], which have the higher spatial coverage of the lunar surface at near-noon illuminations [1]. The first results at this stage are:

1. Effective emissivity values at ~ 2.54 μm are significantly lower (0.60–0.80) in highland-like terrains compared to darker units (0.80–0.90) (Fig. 1).
2. OH/H₂O absorption features are weaker at latitudes between -60° and $+60^\circ$, confirming the previously observed latitudinal trend [3,5] (Fig. 2).
3. Highland-like regions exhibit stronger OH/H₂O signatures than darker units (including the SPA basin as well) at the same latitude for near-noon observations, suggesting a possible link between OH/H₂O retention and optical maturity/surface composition.
4. Copernicus and Langrenus craters appear to be hydroxyl/water rich, in agreement with a TPM-based approach [3] and only partially with [5]. A similar behavior is observed for Proclus crater extended area, west of Crisium.
5. Slightly enhanced hydration is observed near pyroclastic deposits within the area analyzed so far, such as in parts of the Aristarchus Plateau. However, the retrieved values in this area are overall lower than those reported in [5,10], suggesting a lower amount of available water. Hence, further analyses are required to better constrain hydration in pyroclastic deposits using LENNA.

Future analyses will focus on the global-scale diurnal variability of OH/H₂O and on potential relationships between enhanced hydration and lunar surface

properties, including composition, optical maturity, and other surface characteristics.

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Figure 1 Effective spectral emissivity at $\sim 2.54 \mu\text{m}$ modeled with the Hapke's radiative transfer model [9] for the nearside (a) and farside (b). Highland terrains present lower emissivity values if compared to darker units, such as mare-like terrains and pyroclastic deposits.

Figure 2 Espat values defined at $\sim 2.85 \mu\text{m}$ following the workflow presented in [5] for the nearside (a) and farside (b). The results here presented are computed using OP2C M³ data, acquired at near-noon illumination conditions. Results are comparable with [3] and partially in contrast with some results in [5] (e.g., the quantity of OH/H₂O in pyroclastic deposits).